

Cascade Regimes and Corridor Backbones in an Intranational Production Network

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Abstract. We investigate how local disruptions can escalate into systemic economic cascades in an intranational supply network by modeling Indonesia's interregional input–output system as a directed, weighted province–sector production network and simulating threshold cascades with cumulative exposure. Sweeping a single robustness ratio reveals a sharp, system-level transition in cascade outcomes: the same empirical network shifts from a fragile regime, in which large avalanches are common, to a resilient regime, in which cascades typically remain contained, with a narrow near-critical band. Near and beyond the transition, residual systemic hazard condenses into a shrinking set of shock origins. Mechanistically, cascades tend to ignite locally through within-province cross-sector amplification and, when they become systemic, expand rapidly toward a national footprint; cross-province spreading is increasingly suppressed as robustness rises. Aggregating transmissions into corridor networks shows that interprovincial propagation is channeled through a stable mesoscale backbone rather than dispersing uniformly. Corridor roles align with rich-core density and economic scale, indicating a core–periphery transmission structure in which structurally central provinces function as persistent transmitters while many provinces act primarily as receivers. At the functional level, Processing/Manufacturing emerges as the dominant net source in interprovincial sector corridors, highlighting manufacturing-linked activities as key conduits of long-range contagion.

Keywords: intranational MRIO; cascading failures; systemic risk; robustness regimes; corridor networks; core–periphery structure.

1. Introduction

In intranational production systems, shocks originating in a single location or sector may propagate through supply-chain dependencies, resulting in cascading failures distant from the

initial disruption (Acemoglu et al., 2012; Carvalho, 2014). For large, spatially fragmented economies such as archipelagic countries, understanding the transmission of disruptions through domestic production networks is essential for anticipating systemic vulnerability and designing effective containment strategies (Gomez & Mejia, 2025; Li et al., 2025).

Multi-regional input–output (MRIO) tables offer an empirical foundation for analyzing these dynamics by encoding inter-industry transactions across sectors and regions (Isard, 1951; Miller & Blair, 2009), thereby representing the production system as a directed, weighted network of intermediate dependencies (McNerney et al., 2013). However, most MRIO-based assessments are essentially static, relying on proportional transmission logic that fails to capture threshold responses, compounding disruptions, or abrupt regime shifts (Alatristero-Contreras & Fagiolo, 2014; Maulana et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2021). This results in two primary gaps for subnational MRIO networks. First, static structure and centrality do not uniquely determine dynamic cascade outcomes, particularly near critical conditions (Alatristero-Contreras & Fagiolo, 2014; Yue et al., 2024). Second, propagation is often conveyed through scenario-specific impact maps or origin rankings (Gomez et al., 2020), whereas regime-resolved and traffic-weighted descriptions of routing—such as whether cascades repeatedly concentrate on a limited set of geographic and functional conduits and how the stability of these conduits varies with robustness—are less developed.

These gaps are addressed by modeling Indonesia’s interprovincial input–output system as a province–sector production network and simulating deterministic threshold cascades on this empirical structure. The analysis varies a system-wide robustness ratio to map transitions in cascade behavior from fragile to resilient conditions and identifies a near-critical band using a system-level large-cascade probability. The model allows exposure to accumulate across cascade steps, enabling multiple partial disruptions to compound into failure. Building on this regime-resolved perspective, propagation is summarized as recurring province-to-province and sector-to-sector corridors, and the analysis tests whether regime changes primarily rescale traffic on persistent routes or alter the routing skeleton.

The contributions of this study are fourfold. First, a sharp regime shift in avalanche dynamics is documented, and a near-critical operating band is defined. Second, near-critical heterogeneity across province–sector origins is quantified. Third, corridor-network measurements are introduced to reveal routing backbones and persistent source–sink roles across regimes. Fourth, corridor roles are connected to the baseline production network structure and economic scale. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature; Section 3 describes the data and cascade methodology; Section 4 presents the regime transition and origin heterogeneity results; Section 5 analyzes routing mechanisms and corridor–structure alignment; Section 6 discusses implications and limitations; and Section 7 concludes.

2. Literature review

2.1. Shock propagation on economic input–output networks

Input-output (IO) and multi-regional input-output (MRIO) data serve as an empirical foundation for network-based systemic risk analysis, as they capture observed interdependencies among producers and consumers across sectors and locations. Alatristero-

Contreras and Fagiolo (2014) demonstrate that assumptions regarding propagation fundamentally influence system-wide outcomes. Specifically, linear Leontief-style diffusion typically yields large but relatively homogeneous impacts, whereas cascade-type mechanisms that allow nonlinear propagation of disruptions can generate heterogeneous avalanche distributions (Alatrisme-Contreras & Fagiolo, 2014). Consequently, cascade models are particularly appropriate when the objective is to explain origin dependence and disproportionate system-wide amplification, rather than proportional multiplier effects.

2.2. Cascade models, nonlinear regime shifts, and cumulative exposure

To address limitations of proportional transmission, numerous studies represent shock propagation as a nonlinear cascade, where failures reduce interactions and neighboring nodes fail when disruptions surpass a capacity threshold (Lee et al., 2011; Ouyang et al., 2024, 2026; Yue et al., 2024). A key insight from this literature is that systemic responses may display threshold-like shifts as buffering capacity varies. Cascade propagation also need not depend on a single dominant dependency: indirect and multi-step cascades can emerge through the accumulation of disruptions across multiple channels, allowing several partial impacts to combine into a substantial effective shock. This perspective supports the use of exposure-accumulation rules that treat disruption as cumulative across cascade steps rather than as a purely stepwise trigger.

2.3. Intranational MRIO fragility and heterogeneous shock outcomes

While most empirical cascade studies concentrate on national or international economic networks, relatively few investigate intranational cascades using MRIO data. Gómez et al. (2020) contribute to this area by constructing a multilayer intranational MRIO supply-chain network for the United States and simulating threshold cascades to analyze fragility and exposure. Recent intranational multilayer MRIO evidence likewise shows that avalanche outcomes vary strongly with the geographic location and sector of shock origin, and that system response can change sharply as failure thresholds vary (Gomez et al., 2020; Li et al., 2025). This intranational MRIO perspective aligns closely with the present study and underscores the need for analytical tools to identify likely shock transmission routes and assess their stability under varying operating conditions.

2.4. From cascade influence relations to regime-resolved corridor traffic networks

Previous research has constructed derived networks from cascade outcomes, including influence or avalanche relations that connect nodes capable of causing others to fail and reveal mesoscale clustering (Lee et al., 2011; Ouyang et al., 2026). Extending this approach, the present study introduces a regime-resolved, traffic-weighted routing representation for intranational MRIO cascades. Instead of focusing solely on the existence of propagation pathways, this analysis summarizes propagation in terms of recurring province-to-province and sector-to-sector corridors and compares their concentration and stability across different robustness regimes.

3. Data and Method

This section outlines the data and methods used in the study. Figure 1 provides an overview of the workflow, from IRIO-based network construction to cascade simulation and system-level diagnostics.

Fig. 1. Workflow from MRIO data to cascade and routing diagnostics.

3.1. Indonesia MRIO data and node definition

We use the 2016 Indonesian Interregional Input–Output (IRIO) table prepared by Statistics Indonesia (BPS) (Statistics Indonesia (BPS), 2021). The IRIO reports inter-industry transactions across 34 provinces and 17 sectors. We focus on two components: (i) the intermediate transaction matrix Z (million IDR), which records monetary flows of intermediate inputs between province–sector accounts, and (ii) gross output x for each province–sector account. Each province–sector account is represented as a node, yielding $N = 34 \times 17 = 578$ nodes. Gross output $x_{i\alpha}$ is used as the production scale in the cascade threshold rule. While IRIO also reports final demand, our propagation analysis is based on intermediate dependencies encoded in Z and the output scale x .

3.2. Network construction and normalization

We represent the IRIO intermediate transaction block as a directed weighted graph $G = (V, E, W)$ over province–sector accounts. Let $i \in \{1, \dots, 34\}$ index provinces and $\alpha \in \{1, \dots, 17\}$ index sectors. Each node is a province–sector account $\{i, \alpha\}$, so the node set is $V = \{(i, \alpha)\}$

with $|V| = 578$, edge set $E = \{(i, \alpha), (j, \beta) : w_{(i, \alpha), (j, \beta)} > 0\}$, where the edge weight, $w_{(i, \alpha), (j, \beta)} \geq 0$, denote the positive intermediate transaction from node (i, α) to node (j, β) , taken directly from the IRIO intermediate block Z , $w_{ij}^{\alpha\beta} = z_{ij}^{\alpha\beta}$. Collecting all weights yields a supra-adjacency matrix $W = [w_{(i, \alpha), (j, \beta)}] \in \mathbb{R}_+^{N \times N}$. We remove self-loops by setting $w_{(i, \alpha), (i, \alpha)} = 0$. Although the network uses monetary flows, cascade triggering depends on *relative* disruption. In the failure rule, we normalize cumulative disruption by node gross output $x_{i\alpha}$, so thresholds are interpretable as fractions of production capacity of the affected node rather than absolute magnitudes.

3.3. Cascade model and robustness parameter

We simulate shock transmission on the weighted, directed province–sector network using a deterministic threshold cascade model. Our starting point follows the supply-chain cascade framework of Gómez et al. (2020), in which failures propagate when disruption to a node’s trading relations exceeds a buffering capacity proportional to its production. We adapt this framework by accumulating exposure across cascade steps: at each step, a node evaluates the cumulative disruption induced by all nodes that have failed so far, reflecting the idea that multiple partial impacts can combine into a large effective shock (Lee et al 2011).

Let $F(t)$ be the set of nodes failed up to cascade step t , $f_{i\alpha}(t) \in \{0, 1\}$, where $f_{i\alpha}(t) = 1$ indicates the node has failed by step t . A cascade starts by failing one source node at $t = 0$. When a node (j, β) fails, all incidents flow to it (both purchases and sales) are reduced by a fraction c . For a candidate node (i, α) at step t , the cumulative decrement induced by all previously failed nodes is

$$\Delta S_{i\alpha}(t) = c \sum_{(j, \beta) \in F(t)} (w_{ij}^{\alpha\beta} + w_{ji}^{\beta\alpha}) \quad (1)$$

where $c \in (0, 1)$ is shock severity (fractional reduction of flows attached to a failed node). A node fails when this cumulative decrement exceeds its buffer $bx_{i\alpha}$, where $b \in (0, 1)$ is buffering capacity as a fraction of production:

$$\Delta S_{i\alpha}(t) > bx_{i\alpha} \quad (2)$$

Because the failure condition depends only on the ratio $\Omega = b/c$, we treat Ω as a single robustness control; increasing Ω corresponds to stronger buffering relative to shock severity and suppresses cascades. In reduced form, the condition can be written as a normalized disruption threshold:

$$\sum_{(j, \beta) \in F(t)} \frac{(w_{ij}^{\alpha\beta} + w_{ji}^{\beta\alpha})}{x_{i\alpha}} > \Omega \quad (3)$$

A key feature of our implementation is persistence: failure is driven by cumulative decrement from the entire failed set $F(t)$, so multiple partial impacts across successive rounds can combine to exceed the buffer even when no single neighbor is sufficient to trigger collapse. This “persistence” captures limited ability to fully absorb and reset after repeated partial

disruptions, aligning with the intuition that crisis impacts can compound through successive rounds of contagion (Lee et al., 2011; Ouyang et al., 2024). We iterate until no additional nodes satisfy the threshold condition.

3.4. Simulation protocol

For each robustness level Ω , we run a full set of single-source cascade simulations. The protocol is deterministic: given Ω and an initiating source node, the cascade outcome is uniquely determined by the threshold rule. We sweep Ω over 200 log-spaced values in $[0.01, 0.123285]$ and run one single-source cascade per node per Ω . We record avalanche size, depth, and node failure times. These outputs feed the system-level summaries and corridor attribution analyses.

3.5. Measurements and risk metrics

Cascade severity and systemic-event indicator. Avalanche size $A(s, \Omega) \in [0, 1]$ is the fraction of nodes failed at termination (including the initiating origin). We define systemic (large) cascades using threshold τ and use $\tau = 0.05$ unless stated otherwise, with indicator $\mathbb{1}[A(s, \Omega) > \tau]$. Aggregating across all origins yields the system-level large-cascade probability

$$p_\tau(\Omega) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{s=1}^N \mathbb{1}[A(s, \Omega) > \tau] \quad (4)$$

We define the tipping robustness Ω^* where $p_\tau(\Omega^*) \approx 0.5$ and classify robustness regimes as resilient ($p_\tau \leq 0.3$), transition ($0.3 < p_\tau < 0.7$), and fragile ($p_\tau \geq 0.7$).

Persistence across robustness (AUC over $\log \Omega$). Several summaries integrate robustness-response curves over the log-spaced Ω grid using trapezoidal integration of $\int y(\Omega) d\log \Omega$, with an optional normalization by $\Delta \log \Omega$ to yield an average value across the scanned robustness range.

Frontier attribution and corridor construction. To extract dominant transmission channels without double-counting multi-source exposure accumulation, we construct a frontier-attributed backbone: when node j fails at step t , we restrict candidate sources to nodes failed at $t - 1$ and assign the effective source as the frontier node maximizing bilateral exposure. Transmission events are then classified into propagation modes (horizontal, vertical-local, and diagonal) and aggregated into directed province corridor networks. Each corridor $p \rightarrow q$ is weighted by the normalized traffic intensity

$$w_{p \rightarrow q} = \frac{\text{count}(p \rightarrow q)}{N K_{\text{regime}}} \quad (5)$$

and interpreted as the expected number of frontier transmissions from p to q per run within that regime, where K_{regime} is number of Ω points in that regime. Corridor out-strength and in-strength are $s_p^{\text{out}} = \sum_q w_{p \rightarrow q}$ and $s_p^{\text{in}} = \sum_q w_{q \rightarrow p}$; we classify provinces as net sources if $s_p^{\text{out}} > s_p^{\text{in}}$ and net sinks otherwise.

Structural covariates from the baseline production network. To relate corridor roles to static production-network structure, we use provincial rich-core density and total provincial production. Following Maulana et al. (2024), province–sector nodes are classified as rich on the basis of node strength in the weighted directed production network, using seller-based (out-strength) and buyer-based (in-strength) richness thresholds, with the weighted rich-club logic following Alstott et al. (2014). Provincial rich-core density is defined as the share of province–sector nodes within a province that are classified as rich under the chosen threshold rule.

4. Phase transition and heterogeneity

4.1. Regime shift and critical point

We characterize cascade dynamics by sweeping robustness $\Omega \in [0.01, 0.123285]$ and measuring avalanche size A , defined as the fraction of province–sector nodes that fail by the end of a single-source cascade. Avalanche-size distributions exhibit a sharp regime shift (Fig. 2a). At low robustness, the exceedance probability $P(A > a)$ remains close to one until a approaches unity, indicating that many shocks escalate into very large cascades (fragile regime). As Ω increases into an intermediate band ($\Omega \approx 0.03$ – 0.06), exceedance probabilities drop rapidly, marking an abrupt suppression of tail risk (transition regime). At higher robustness ($\Omega \gtrsim 0.08$), large avalanches become rare and most cascades die out locally (resilient regime).

Fig. 2. Regime shift in cascade size as robustness varies. (a) CCDFs of avalanche size A for selected Ω . (b) Mean and median A across origins and the large-cascade probability $p_\tau(\Omega)$ ($\tau = 0.05$); Ω^* and the near-critical band are indicated.

Figure 2b summarizes this transition using the mean and median of A across all shock origins. The median collapses over a narrow interval, showing that typical cascades switch quickly from system-wide to negligible as robustness increases. The mean declines more gradually, indicating persistent heterogeneity: even after typical cascades become small, a minority of origins continue to trigger disproportionately large events. We operationalize the tipping point using a large-cascade criterion τ and define $p_\tau(\Omega) = P(A > \tau)$. With $\tau = 0.05$, we identify $\Omega^* \approx 0.0432$ via $p_\tau(\Omega^*) \approx 0.5$ and define a near-critical band where $p_\tau(\Omega) \in [0.3, 0.7]$ (Fig. 2b). The regime-shift conclusion is robust to alternative cascade criteria (SI Fig. 1).

Finally, near and beyond the transition, systemic risk becomes increasingly concentrated in a shrinking set of origins. Figure 3 shows that the share of total expected impact attributable to

the top 1–10% of origins rises strongly with Ω , even as the number of origins capable of exceeding large-cascade thresholds declines. This condensation is extreme at the highest robustness studied: only a handful of province–sector origins still generate system-wide cascades ($A = 1$; Table SI 1), highlighting a regime where overall vulnerability is reduced but residual systemic hazard is dominated by a few catastrophic triggers.

Fig. 3. Concentration of cascade impacts across shock origins as Ω increases. (a) Top- k share of total mean avalanche size. (b) Number of origins exceeding $A \geq 0.05$, $A \geq 0.5$, and $A = 1$.

4.2. Near-critical heterogeneity

Near the tipping point Ω^* , cascade outcomes exhibit strong dependence on their origin. Figure 4 presents the mean avalanche size by province–sector origin at Ω^* , revealing substantial heterogeneity along both dimensions. Certain provinces consistently demonstrate higher average cascade potential across sectors, while several sectors display elevated averages across multiple provinces

The heatmap reveals pronounced hot spots and gaps that cannot be accounted for by province or sector averages alone, indicating strong province-sector specificity. The same sector may be cascade-capable in certain provinces but comparatively benign in others, and vice versa (Table SI 2). This specificity is also evident in tail risk, as exceedance probabilities vary widely across origins even at fixed Ω^* (SI Fig. 2). The nature of heterogeneity shifts across regimes: in the fragile regime, many origins generate large cascades while some remain low-impact; in the resilient regime, most origins die out rapidly, but a small subset continues to exhibit cascade capability (SI Figs. 3–4).

Fig. 4. Mean avalanche size by shock origin at the critical point Ω^* . Heatmap shows average A for each province–sector origin; color uses a logit scale of A ; marginal bars show province and sector means.

4.3. Persistence across robustness

Near-critical maps identify key actors at Ω^* , although the system’s buffering effectiveness depends on policy, inventory levels, substitution options, and the severity of disruptions. To determine which groups remain cascade-capable beyond a single operating point, each province and sector is ranked using a persistence score derived from the area under its robustness–response curve (AUC), which summarizes the mean avalanche size across the scanned Ω range (Fig. 5).

Sector rankings exhibit greater differentiation than province rankings (Fig. 5), suggesting that functional roles provide a more persistent ordering of cascade potential than geographic location. Processing Industry (manufacturing), Construction, Wholesale and Retail Trade, and Transportation and Warehousing dominate the AUC list, underscoring a limited set of functions that remain influential across varying operating conditions. Province rankings display weaker separation, consistent with aggregation across heterogeneous sectors; however, the top tier still

identifies where cascade-capable origins are prevalent across robustness levels. Rank stability across regimes is summarized in Table SI 3.

At the provincial level, the top AUC tier includes East Java, South Sulawesi, Jakarta, Banten, North Sumatra, and West Papua (Fig. 5a). Although Java-based provinces predominate, the inclusion of North Sumatra (Sumatra Island in western Indonesia), South Sulawesi (Sulawesi Island in central Indonesia), and West Papua (Papua Island in eastern Indonesia) demonstrates that persistent cascade-capable origins are not limited to Java, but also cluster in hub provinces on other major islands.

A social and economic system constitutes a complex system in which the adaptive capacity of the economy allows it to identify mechanisms for shifting critical threshold points. As shown in Figure 5b, where the persistence score of the manufacturing sector ($AUC = 1.75$) is particularly high, inventories tend to face considerable difficulty in securing alternative sources of supply. At the provincial level, given Indonesia's archipelagic geography, the dominance of economic process and activity in East Java and Jakarta remains substantial, supported by their large output scale, and it would take a relatively long time for other provinces to substitute for their role in the short run. From the perspective of robustness in complex systems, "macro-level panic" is likely to remain a valid phenomenon regardless of the agility of economic agents.

If cascade influence is concentrated within specific functions and a subset of provinces, it is likely to also be concentrated in the routes through which cascades propagate. The following section examines propagation footprints, transmission modes, and the corridor or backbone structures that organize interprovincial and intersectoral transmission.

Fig. 5. Persistence ranking across robustness. Top-15 (a) provinces and (b) sectors by AUC of group-mean avalanche size integrated over $\log \Omega$.

5. Corridor routing and mesoscale backbone

5.1. Spatial propagation footprints

Cascading failures may result from cumulative exposure to multiple upstream disruptions. To illustrate propagation dynamics, failure-time footprints are used to depict the spatial and temporal spread of cascades (Fig. 6). Figure 6 presents near-critical cascades initiated in the Processing/Manufacturing sector at Ω^* ($\tau = 0.05$) for three representative origin provinces.

In most cases, early propagation (25–50% of cascade duration) remains localized, with failures concentrated within and near the origin province. This pattern reflects strong within-province

amplification, where closely interconnected local sectors accumulate disruptions rapidly before interprovincial transmission prevails. As cascades approach 75–100% of their duration, the affected footprint often expands abruptly to a national scale. Late-stage maps exhibit visual similarity even when early footprints differ, indicating that near Ω^* , the set of ultimately vulnerable provinces is determined primarily by the network-wide structure, while the origin province influences the timing and manner of cascade initiation.

To quantify the progression from local to national impact, the mean distances of provinces affected early (\bar{d}_{early}) and late (\bar{d}_{late}) in each cascade are compared. The local-first index, $\text{LFI} = \bar{d}_{\text{late}} - \bar{d}_{\text{early}}$, increases from resilient to transition to fragile robustness regimes (Table SI 4), demonstrating that reduced robustness leads to cascades that more frequently reach provinces distant from the origin. Long-range spreading primarily occurs in the late stages: late long-jumps are common even in resilient regimes and become nearly universal in transition and fragile regimes, while early long-jumps remain relatively rare (Table SI 4). These findings are consistent across alternative long-jump distance thresholds (Table SI 5). The following section relates these footprint patterns to transmission mechanisms by decomposing cascades into propagation modes and corridor traffic.

Fig. 6. Spatial propagation footprints at criticality $\Omega^* \approx 0.0432$ ($\tau = 0.05$) for Processing-sector shocks in three provinces: Jakarta, South Sulawesi, North Sumatra. Rows show snapshots at 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% of cascade duration; province shading indicates failed node counts aggregated to provinces.

5.2. Propagation mode

Dominant transmission channels are summarized by decomposing attributed parent-child events into three propagation modes (Fig. 7). Across all regimes, propagation is dominated by vertical-local events, defined as events occurring within the same province but across different sectors. This pattern indicates that cascades are primarily amplified through cross-sector coupling within provinces.

With increasing robustness, diagonal long-range transmission, defined as events spanning different provinces and sectors, declines from approximately 0.38 to 0.29 to 0.21 across the fragile, transition, and resilient regimes, respectively. In contrast, vertical-local transmission rises from approximately 0.56 to 0.66 to 0.75. Horizontal same-sector cross-province events remain consistently low, ranging from approximately 0.04 to 0.06. These mode shares collectively demonstrate that greater robustness suppresses cross-province contagion within the dominant backbone, resulting in a more localized propagation profile. Absolute event volumes and detailed regime shares are provided in Table SI 6. These results prompt further investigation into the specific province-to-province routes through which interprovincial contagion is concentrated when it does occur.

Fig. 7. Composition of frontier-attributed transmission modes by robustness regime. Stacked bars show the shares of horizontal, vertical-local, and diagonal transmission events.

5.3. Corridor networks

5.3.1. Province corridor networks

To identify the concentration of interprovincial contagion, cascade transmissions are aggregated into a directed province corridor network. Figure 8a presents the corridor backbone during the transition regime, a phase in which interprovincial propagation is active but not yet saturated. The visualization reveals pronouncedly uneven routing: a small subset of corridors accounts for a disproportionate share of transmission, and provinces are differentiated into net sources (exporters of corridor traffic) and net sinks (receivers). This corridor-based perspective extends the propagation-mode findings by demonstrating that cross-province contagion is channeled through a limited number of conduits, rather than being distributed uniformly across all province pairs.

The fundamental structure of the corridor network remains broadly stable across regimes, even as overall traffic increases. Table 1 indicates that the corridor network is relatively dense and reciprocal in all regimes, with both density and reciprocity reaching their highest levels in the fragile regime. Corridor traffic and node strengths increase markedly with fragility: median out-strength rises from 0.08 (resilient) to 0.38 (transition) to 0.93 (fragile), while median in-strength increases from 0.51 to 2.98 to 6.20. Inequality in out-strength and edge weights remains high (Gini coefficient approximately 0.76–0.79), reflecting a persistent concentration

of transmission along a backbone. Supporting this, Figure 8b demonstrates substantial overlap in dominant corridor sets across regimes, with the greatest similarity observed between transition and fragile conditions (Jaccard index 0.76; overlap coefficient 0.87). These findings suggest that regime changes primarily rescale traffic along largely persistent routes, rather than fundamentally altering the routing structure.

Fig. 8. Province corridor routing and cross-regime similarity. (a) Transition-regime province corridor network (edge width = corridor intensity; node size = out-strength; color = net source/sink). (b) Pairwise overlap of top 30 corridors sets across regimes (Jaccard; overlap coefficient in parentheses).

Table 1. Summary statistics of province corridor networks by robustness regime ($\tau = 0.05$): density, reciprocity, and distribution summaries (median, Gini) for out-strength, in-strength, and edge weights.

Regime	Density	Reciprocity	Out-strength		In-strength		Weight	
			Median	Gini	Median	Gini	Median	Gini
Resilient	0.55	0.63	0.08	0.76	0.51	0.23	0.00	0.78
Transition	0.55	0.63	0.38	0.78	2.98	0.18	0.03	0.77
Fragile	0.73	0.80	0.93	0.79	6.20	0.13	0.04	0.79

The source–sink decomposition identifies which provinces function as net transmitters or net receivers in corridor routing (Table 2). Jakarta consistently emerges as the primary source across all regimes. Other significant sources are predominantly located in Java, with additional hub provinces outside Java, such as East Kalimantan, South Sumatra, North Sumatra, and South Sulawesi, particularly evident in the transition regime. The identity of sink provinces varies more substantially across regimes, indicating shifts in corridor traffic accumulation under different operating conditions. Comprehensive province rankings and net-strength values are provided in Table SI 8, while the leading province-to-province corridors for each regime are detailed in Table SI 7.

The corridor analysis is subsequently conducted at the functional level by aggregating interprovincial transmissions into sector corridors to determine which economic functions predominate in long-range propagation.

Table 2. Top 10 net source and net sink provinces by robustness regime, ranked by net corridor balance.

Rank	Source			Sink		
	Resilience	Transition	Fragile	Resilience	Transition	Fragile
1	Jakarta	Jakarta	Jakarta	Papua	Aceh	West Nusa Tenggara
2	East Java	Banten	Banten	West Sulawesi	West Nusa Tenggara	Bangka Belitung Islands
3	Banten	East Java	East Java	East Nusa Tenggara	Gorontalo	Aceh
4	East Kalimantan	East Kalimantan	East Kalimantan	Gorontalo	West Sulawesi	Gorontalo
5	South Sumatra	South Sumatra	South Sumatra	North Maluku	East Nusa Tenggara	West Sulawesi
6	North Sumatra	North Sumatra	North Sumatra	West Nusa Tenggara	Bengkulu	Maluku
7	Central Java	South Sulawesi	South Sulawesi	Maluku	Bangka Belitung Islands	Bengkulu
8	Riau	Riau	Riau	South Kalimantan	Papua	Riau Islands
9	Central Sulawesi	West Java	West Java	Aceh	Maluku	East Nusa Tenggara
10	West Java	Central Java	Central Java	North Sulawesi	North Maluku	Papua

5.3.2. Sectoral corridor networks and functional routing

In addition to province–province routing, interprovincial transmission traffic is aggregated into a directed sector corridor network for each robustness regime. Table 3 demonstrates that this functional routing network is already topologically dense in the resilient regime (density 0.65; reciprocity 0.70) and becomes marginally denser and more reciprocal as fragility increases (density 0.77; reciprocity 0.79). Although the set of feasible sector-to-sector routes remains broad across all regimes, transmission intensity increases substantially with fragility: median out-strength rises from 0.18 (resilient) to 0.78 (transition) to 2.39 (fragile), and median in-strength from 0.81 to 5.25 to 11.54. Despite this intensification, edge-weight inequality remains extremely high (weight Gini \approx 0.85–0.86), suggesting that cross-province contagion primarily scales through repeated activation of a limited set of functional conduits rather than uniform distribution across all sector pairs.

Table 3. Summary statistics of interprovincial sector corridor networks by robustness regime: density, reciprocity, and distribution summaries (median, Gini) for out-strength, in-strength, and edge weights.

Regime	Density	Reciprocity	Out-strength		In-strength		Weight	
			Median	Gini	Median	Gini	Median	Gini
Resilient	0.65	0.70	0.18	0.80	0.81	0.34	0.00	0.86
Transition	0.67	0.76	0.78	0.81	5.25	0.25	0.02	0.86
Fragile	0.77	0.79	2.39	0.79	11.54	0.18	0.05	0.85

Table 4 indicates a pronounced asymmetric source–sink structure in functional routing. The Processing Industry consistently serves as the dominant net source across all regimes, with its

net strength increasing by more than an order of magnitude from resilient to fragile (8.90 to 55.67 to 122.47), establishing it as the primary driver of interprovincial contagion. Conversely, most other sectors function as net sinks, exhibiting increasingly negative net strength as fragility rises. This pattern aligns with systemic cascades accumulating within a broad range of downstream and service functions rather than being re-exported (for example, Healthcare Services reaches -14.91 in the fragile regime). A limited number of regime-dependent exceptions are observed, such as Mining transitioning from a marginal source in the resilient regime to a sink in the transition and fragile regimes, and Company Services emerging as a source in the transition and fragile regimes. The principal sector-to-sector “highways” underlying these patterns are detailed in Table SI 9.

Table 4. Sector sources and sinks by robustness regime in the interprovincial sector corridor network, ranked by net corridor balance.

sector	Resilient		Transition		Fragile	
	role	Net strength	role	Net strength	role	Net strength
Processing Industry	source	8.90	source	55.67	source	122.47
Mining	source	0.07	sink	-0.11	sink	-1.11
Real Estate	sink	-0.03	sink	-0.59	sink	-3.01
Company Services	sink	-0.04	source	1.37	source	2.83
Wholesale and Retail Trade	sink	-0.08	sink	-2.43	sink	-5.86
Construction	sink	-0.30	sink	-4.17	sink	-8.31
Information and Communication	sink	-0.44	sink	-3.16	sink	-7.42
Government Administration	sink	-0.46	sink	-3.57	sink	-8.93
Accommodation	sink	-0.56	sink	-3.87	sink	-8.66
Financial Services	sink	-0.56	sink	-2.92	sink	-8.11
Other Services	sink	-0.58	sink	-4.10	sink	-10.07
Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries	sink	-0.76	sink	-5.06	sink	-10.04
Education Services	sink	-0.80	sink	-5.23	sink	-11.53
Water Supply/ Management/ Recycling	sink	-0.98	sink	-5.39	sink	-12.25
Electricity/Gas Supply	sink	-0.99	sink	-4.25	sink	-6.81
Transportation and Warehousing	sink	-1.09	sink	-5.07	sink	-8.28
Healthcare Services	sink	-1.31	sink	-7.10	sink	-14.91

After characterizing both geographic (province) and functional (sector) routing backbones, the next step is to assess how corridor roles correspond to the baseline production-network structure and economic scale.

5.4. Corridor–structure alignment and structural correlates

The corridor networks (Fig. 8) demonstrate that propagation is spatially heterogeneous. A small subset of provinces consistently functions as net transmitters, whereas many provinces primarily serve as receivers. This observation raises an alignment question: do these dynamic corridor roles correspond to static structures in the underlying province–sector production network and to fundamental measures of economic scale?

Figure 9 illustrates this relationship within the transition regime. Provinces exhibiting higher rich-core density generally assume positive net corridor roles (net sources), while those with lower rich-core density tend to function as net sinks. A comparable separation emerges when net corridor role is plotted against total provincial output, as economically larger provinces are more likely to act as net transmitters and smaller provinces as net receivers. This broader interpretation is consistent with cross-country IO evidence showing that more interconnected economies and more globally central sectors tend to generate larger avalanches (Alatríste-Contreras & Fagiolo, 2014).

Fig. 9 Corridor-role alignment with structure and scale at transition regime. Net corridor role vs (a) rich-core density and (b) total provincial output; points are colored by net source/sink, with selected top sources labeled. (Symlog y-axis; log x-axis in panel b.)

These patterns extend beyond the transition regime. The association between net corridor role and rich-core density remains strong across robustness regimes and persists under alternative rich-core definitions and percentile cutoffs (Table SI 10). Net corridor role also exhibits a strong correlation with economic scale, measured by total output and value added, in all regimes (Table SI 11). Collectively, these findings suggest that robustness primarily affects the intensity of corridor traffic, whereas the distinction between persistent transmitters and receivers is determined by stable core–periphery structure and size-related asymmetries in the baseline production network.

6. Discussion

The use of the 2016 interregional input–output table may raise concerns about how precisely the findings reflect current economic realities, insofar as the systemic risk simulation is temporally grounded in an economic structure that dates back a decade. Since 2016, post-pandemic supply chain restructuring, infrastructure expansion outside Java, and various capital transitions have reshaped the economy. Nevertheless, it is important to emphasize that although the specific details of social structures may evolve over time, social complexity generally converges toward broader structural configurations that tend to remain stable. This can be associated with the empirical persistence of topological stability, or structural inertia, within production networks.

In general, this study demonstrates that cascading failures within an intranational province–sector production network display nonlinear regime behavior and structured routing, with implications extending beyond static exposure or centrality. Varying a single robustness ratio reveals a distinct, system-level transition in the frequency of large cascades, highlighting that systemic cascading risk emerges from the network’s collective dynamics rather than the performance of individual provinces or sectors. The empirical province–sector network can function as either broadly fragile, where large cascades frequently occur, or broadly resilient, where such events are rare. A narrow intermediate band exists in which the system exhibits maximal sensitivity, and minor adjustments in buffering or shock severity can lead to disproportionately large changes in systemic outcomes. Within this transition band, outcomes are highly origin-dependent, consistent with recent multilayer evidence showing that shock effects vary strongly by both originating province and sector (Gomez et al., 2020; Li et al., 2025). Accordingly, the results are organized around operational regimes, reporting patterns that are comparable across different conditions, such as the expansion of spatial footprints, shifts in transmission modes, and changes in corridor traffic concentration as robustness varies. This approach extends previous IO-network and cascade studies by explicitly defining and comparing operating regimes across robustness conditions under a common propagation mechanism.

The routing analysis elucidates the mechanisms by which shocks propagate. Cascades typically originate locally and, upon becoming systemic, expand rapidly to encompass a national footprint. Propagation-mode decomposition reveals that early amplification is primarily driven by within-province, cross-sector interactions, whereas long-range dissemination is predominantly facilitated by cross-province, cross-sector events. As system robustness increases, the prevalence of these long-range events diminishes. At the mesoscale, corridor network analysis indicates that interprovincial propagation is channeled through a limited set of province-to-province conduits and sector-to-sector pathways, rather than occurring diffusely.

Across different regimes, changes in propagation resemble shifts in traffic volume rather than alterations to the underlying routing map. Corridor intensity increases and reciprocity may rise as the system transitions from resilient to fragile conditions, yet dominant conduits remain identifiable. This pattern indicates that robustness primarily reduces systemic risk by limiting repeated use of the interprovincial backbone, rather than by removing routes entirely. The routing skeleton remains relatively stable, while robustness determines the volume of traffic it can accommodate during cascading events.

These dynamic patterns align with the static mesoscale organization of Indonesia’s production network, in which production typically forms spatially cohesive, multi-sector clusters, while cross-island exchange is facilitated by a limited number of rich-core hubs and connectors (Maulana et al., 2024). In this context, local ignition results from dense coupling within clusters, whereas national spread becomes probable when disruptions reach the connectors that integrate modules across the archipelago. The prominence of processing and manufacturing

within sector corridors supports this logic, as manufacturing-linked functions often mediate exchanges between spatial blocks and thus serve as natural bridges for long-range propagation under stress.

The findings indicate two complementary approaches to prevention for regional development and resilience (Fu et al., 2026). The first is a topology-aware development strategy that promotes polycentric growth and buffered integration (Maulana et al., 2025). This strategy involves reinforcing multiple regional cores beyond the current concentration and linking them through a limited number of redundant, well-resourced inter-core connections, thereby supporting growth without transforming the national network into an unbuffered channel for long-range contagion. The second approach is a targeted hardening strategy that addresses critical components identified by cascade routing, such as key transmitter provinces, high-traffic interprovincial corridors, and functional highways that facilitate cross-region exchange. This is achieved through continuity planning, provision of slack capacity, and rapid-recovery measures. Additionally, understanding corridor source–sink roles enhances monitoring and preparedness, with transmitter provinces prioritized for early warning, escalation management, and containment, and receiver provinces prioritized for readiness against imported disruptions (Li et al., 2025).

At the pattern level, the principal conclusions remain robust. The regime transition is consistent across cascade criteria, the local-first followed by long-range signature persists under alternative distance thresholds, and routing continues to concentrate around identifiable conduits as traffic intensifies. However, precise rankings and marginal corridor identities may vary depending on threshold selection and aggregation methods. This analysis is subject to several limitations. It relies on a single-year MRIO snapshot, omits adaptive responses such as substitution, inventory adjustments, price changes, and recovery processes, and considers robustness as system-wide within a single simulation (Fu et al., 2026). While corridor attribution offers a concise summary of dominant channels, it does not imply unique causality. Future research should extend the framework to incorporate heterogeneous buffering, adaptive dynamics, multi-year evolution, and event-based validation (Li et al., 2025).

7. Conclusion

Combined regime mapping and corridor-network analysis demonstrate that cascades in Indonesia's province–sector production network exhibit a sharp transition as robustness increases and are routed through a concentrated mesoscale backbone. Analysis of the system-wide robustness ratio identifies fragile, near-critical, and resilient regimes, with systemic risk becoming most dependent on the origin near the tipping region, where small differences in the initiating province–sector distinguish between contained failures and system-wide cascades.

Propagation is primarily driven by within-province cross-sector amplification, whereas long-range interprovincial spread occurs mainly through cross-province, cross-sector events and is increasingly suppressed as robustness increases. Corridor networks translate this mechanism into regime-comparable routing patterns, characterized by persistent source–sink roles and stable dominant conduits, indicating that robustness mainly rescales traffic on persistent routes rather than completely altering the routing structure. Furthermore, the alignment between

corridor roles, rich-core density, and economic scale offers an interpretable connection from the baseline MRIO structure to observed cascade routing.

Author contributions

Ardian Maulana: Synthesized data, performed analysis, created tables and figures, discussed the results, and contributed to the final manuscript. Hokky Situngkir: Supervised the research, discussed the results, and contributed to the final manuscript. Pradono Pradono: Supervised the research, discussed the results, and contributed to the final manuscript. Adiwah Fahlan Aritenang: Supervised the research, Discussed the results and contributed to the final manuscript.

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Data Availability

The dataset supporting the conclusions of this article is available in the GitHub repository, <https://github.com/ardianeff/2016irioindonesia.git>.

Declarations

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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Appendices

Fig. SI. 1. Phase diagram of avalanche tail probability. Heatmap of $P(A > a)$ over robustness Ω and avalanche-size threshold a ; color indicates $P(A > a)$.

Table SI. 1. Province–sector origins that generate system-wide cascades ($A = 1$) at $\Omega = 0.123285$, with baseline gross output (in Million IDR).

Province	Sector	Avalanche size	Node gross output
East Kalimantan	Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries	1	53114138
East Kalimantan	Processing Industry	1	244275033
East Kalimantan	Mining	1	335435331
East Java	Wholesale and Retail Trade	1	376866220
Jakarta Province	Construction	1	737465601
East Java	Processing Industry	1	1237843510

Fig. SI. 2. CCDF heterogeneity near criticality. (a) CCDFs of avalanche size A by origin province.

Fig. SI. 3. Province–sector heatmap in the fragile regime. Mean avalanche size A by origin province (rows) and origin sector (columns) at $\Omega = 0.020022$ ($\tau = 0.05$); color uses a logit scale of A . Marginal bars show row and column means.

Fig. SI. 4. Province–sector heatmap in the resilient regime. Mean avalanche size A by origin province (rows) and origin sector (columns) at $\Omega = 0.0994757$ ($\tau = 0.05$); color uses the same logit scale of A as Fig. SI 3. Marginal bars show row and column means.

Table SI. 2. Variance shares for the province-sector mean avalanche-size matrix at $\Omega^* = 0.0432422$ ($\tau = 0.05$): province (row means), sector (column means), and interaction (residual).

Component	Variance share
Province (row means)	0.344
Sector (col means)	0.267
Interaction (residual)	0.388

Table SI. 3. Concordance between global persistence ranking and regime-specific persistence ranking for provinces and sectors: Spearman correlation and top- k overlap by regime.

Regime		Correlation (global vs regime)	Top k overlap with global
Province	Resilient ($p_\tau \leq 0.3$)	0.838	7/10
	Transition ($0.3 < p_\tau < 0.7$)	0.840	7/10
	Fragile ($p_\tau \geq 0.7$)	0.364	5/10
Sector	Resilient ($p_\tau \leq 0.3$)	0.982	7/8

	Transition ($0.3 < p_{\tau} < 0.7$)	0.985	8/8
	Fragile ($p_{\tau} \geq 0.7$)	0.903	7/8

Table SI. 4. Local-first vs long-jump propagation summary by regime ($\tau = 0.05$): number of runs, mean LFI, share of runs with positive LFI, and early/late long-jump shares (800 km).

Regime	# runs	LFI mean [95% CI]	% runs (LFI > 0)	% Early long jump (800 km)	% Late long jump (≥ 800 km)
Resilient	4659	963 [940, 987]	84.7	35.6	85.8
Transition	14174	1362 [1350, 1374]	93.4	28.5	98.7
Fragile	41619	1,658 [1652, 1664]	98.5	23	98.4

Table SI. 5. Long-jump shares by regime under alternative distance thresholds (300 km, 500 km, 800 km), with LFI reported for reference. Early/late fixed at early=5, late=5)

Regime	LFI mean (km)	Early long- jump share (300 km)	Early (500 km)	Early (800 km)	Late long- jump share (300 km)	Late (500 km)	Late (800 km)
Resilient	963	76.1%	55.5%	35.6%	96.6%	93.5%	85.8%
Transition	1,362	75.8%	54.0%	28.5%	99.9%	99.6%	98.7%
Fragile	1,658	72.7%	47.6%	23.0%	99.9%	99.7%	98.4%

Table SI. 6. Propagation-mode volumes and shares by regime counts and percentages for horizontal, vertical-local, and diagonal transmission events, and total events.

Regime	Horizontal (diff prov, same sector)	Vertical-local (same prov, diff sector)	Diagonal (diff prov, diff sector)	Total propagation events
fragile	1.41M (5.85%)	13.42M (55.73%)	9.25M (38.42%)	24.08M
transition	0.42M (5.11%)	5.49M (66.25%)	2.37M (28.64%)	8.28M
resilient	0.12M (4.43%)	1.95M (75.04%)	0.53M (20.54%)	2.60M

Table SI. 7. Top 10 province-to-province corridors by regime, listed as directed source to target province pairs ranked by corridor intensity.

Resilient		Transition		Fragile	
Source	Target	Source	Target	Source	Target
Jakarta	Gorontalo	Jakarta	Gorontalo	Jakarta	Gorontalo
Jakarta	East Nusa Tenggara	Jakarta	West Nusa Tenggara	Jakarta	West Nusa Tenggara
East Kalimantan	South Kalimantan	Jakarta	Bangka Belitung Islands	Jakarta	Bangka Belitung Islands
Jakarta	West Nusa Tenggara	Banten	Lampung	Jakarta	Aceh
North Sumatra	Aceh	Jakarta	Aceh	Jakarta	East Nusa Tenggara

Banten	Papua	Jakarta	East Nusa Tenggara	Jakarta	Jambi
Banten	West Sulawesi	Jakarta	West Sumatra	Jakarta	West Sumatra
East Kalimantan	North Sulawesi	Jakarta	Jambi	Jakarta	Bengkulu
East Java	Papua	Jakarta Province	Bengkulu	Banten	Lampung
Jakarta	North Maluku	East Kalimantan	South Kalimantan	Jakarta	Central Sulawesi

Table SI. 8. Top 10 Source and sink provinces by regime. Provinces are listed with role (source/sink) and net strength for resilient, transition, and fragile regimes.

Province	Resilient		Transition		Fragile	
	Role	Net strength	Role	Net strength	Role	Net strength
Jakarta	source	3.88	source	29.92	source	69.26
East Java	source	2.73	source	12.00	source	20.58
Banten	source	1.99	source	12.68	source	21.67
East Kalimantan	source	1.54	source	8.48	source	15.08
South Sumatra	source	1.21	source	3.13	source	5.96
North Sumatra	source	0.85	source	2.86	source	4.81
Central Java	source	0.40	source	0.08	source	0.17
Riau	source	0.21	source	0.77	source	2.96
Central Sulawesi	source	0.14	sink	-0.58	sink	-0.57
West Java	source	0.11	source	0.22	source	0.81
Jambi	sink	-0.15	sink	-2.70	sink	-5.42
South Sulawesi	sink	-0.17	source	1.23	source	3.58
North Sulawesi	sink	-0.58	sink	-2.14	sink	-5.05
Aceh	sink	-0.60	sink	-4.52	sink	-8.14
South Kalimantan	sink	-0.61	sink	-2.79	sink	-5.70
Maluku	sink	-0.66	sink	-3.41	sink	-7.28
West Nusa Tenggara	sink	-0.79	sink	-4.32	sink	-8.57
North Maluku	sink	-0.80	sink	-3.24	sink	-6.31
Gorontalo	sink	-0.82	sink	-4.09	sink	-8.11
East Nusa Tenggara	sink	-0.85	sink	-3.75	sink	-6.79
West Sulawesi	sink	-0.89	sink	-3.86	sink	-7.45
Papua	sink	-0.92	sink	-3.51	sink	-6.75

Table SI. 9. Top 10 interprovincial sector-to-sector corridors by regime, listed as directed source to target sector pairs ranked by corridor intensity.

Resilience		Transition		Fragile	
Source	Target	Source	Target	Source	Target
Mining	Electricity/ Gas Supply	Processing Industry	Healthcare Services	Processing Industry	Healthcare Services
Processing Industry	Transportation and Warehousing	Processing Industry	Transportation and Warehousing	Processing Industry	Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries

Table SI. 11. Spearman correlations between province net corridor role and economic scale (total output; value added), reported by regime.

Regime	Total output	P value	Value added	P value
resilient	0.78	7.24E-08	0.76	1.87E-07
transition	0.74	5.70E-07	0.73	8.53E-07
fragile	0.76	2.40E-07	0.75	3.96E-07